

Title: LGBTQ+ Climate and Disaster Resilience Survey Instrument

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Notes about this survey: This survey instrument was developed as part of a project called “Assessing and enhancing climate resilience of LGBTQIA+ populations in Ohio”. The project aims to identify climate-related challenges and disaster resilience among LGBTQIA+ populations across Ohio and to explore how resilience intersects with housing and health outcomes among LGBTQIA+ communities. The survey focuses on experiences of flooding and extreme heat, as these are the climate-related hazards that are most relevant for Ohio. The survey contains the following sections: demographics, housing, experience of natural hazards (heat and flooding), and emergency services.

This instrument was deployed in an online survey conducted among LGBTQIA+ residents in Ohio from November to December 2024. The survey was administered by Centiment, a third-party research platform. Centiment gathered responses from LGBTQIA+ adults living in Ohio and delivered the results when a sample size of over 900 was reached.

In publishing this survey, the research team hopes that others will find the questions useful. Anyone may implement this survey in full or in part in other settings to collect rich data about LGBTQIA+ climate and disaster resilience. The survey could be directly applied to locations exposed to heat and flooding or the specific hazards could be adjusted depending on the context.

The survey could also be improved and expanded. For additional geographic information, the survey could include a question about respondent ZIP Code. Additional questions about housing, health, discrimination, or other outcomes could be added depending on the research questions

and survey resources/ desired length. For example, additional questions could be asked to evaluate the general experiences of LGBTQIA+ respondents within their local contexts (political context, challenges in accessing gender affirming care, access to queer spaces and community, etc.). The research team is happy to brainstorm with anyone who may be interested in expanding the survey instrument.

LGBTQ+ Climate and Disaster Resilience Survey Instrument

Demographics

[RACE] Which best describes your race/ethnicity? Check all that apply.

- American Indian, Alaska native or First Nations
- Asian
- Black or African American
- Hispanic or Latinx
- Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
- Middle Eastern or North African
- White
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[GENDER] What is your current gender identity? [Select one.]

- Cisgender woman
- Cisgender man
- Transgender woman
- Transgender man
- Non-binary or gender queer
- I have another gender identity, which is _____.
- I prefer not to answer.

[SEXUALITY] Which of the following best describes you?

- Heterosexual or Straight
- Gay
- Lesbian
- Bisexual
- Pansexual
- Asexual
- Queer
- Two-Spirit

- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[AGE] How old are you?

- Under 18
- 18-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55-64 years old
- 65+ years old

[EDUCATION] What is your highest level of education?

- Less than High School
- High school (including GED)
- Some college (no degree)
- Technical certification
- Associate degree (2-year)
- Bachelor's degree (4-year)
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree
- Professional degree (JD, MD)
- Prefer not to say

[EMPLOYMENT] What is your employment status?

- Full-time
- Part-time
- Contract or temporary
- Retired
- Student
- Unemployed
- Unable to work
- Other (please specify)
- Prefer not to answer

[INCOME] What is your annual household income?

- \$0-\$29,999
- \$30,000-\$59,999
- \$60,000-\$89,999
- \$90,000-\$119,999

- \$120,000+
- Prefer not to answer

[DISABILITY] Do you identify as a person with a disability or other chronic condition?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to answer

IF YES

[DISABILITY2] How would you describe your disability or chronic condition? Select all that apply.

- Attention deficit
- Autism
- Blind or visually impaired
- Deaf or hard of hearing
- Health-related disability
- Learning disability
- Mental health condition
- Mobility-related disability
- Speech-related disability
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

Housing

[GEOGRAPHY] How would you describe the neighborhood where you live? If you are unsure, please select to describe your neighborhood in more detail (e.g., zip code, town name, etc.)

- Urban
- Suburban
- Rural
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[TENURE] Do you currently own or rent the place where you live?

- Own
- Rent
- Live with Family/ Chosen Family
- Prefer to describe:

- Prefer not to answer

[AFFORDABILITY] Have you ever had difficulty finding affordable housing in your area?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[INSECURITY] Have you ever experienced housing insecurity (not having stable or adequate living arrangements)?

- Yes- currently experiencing housing insecurity
- Yes- experienced housing insecurity in the past but currently housing secure
- No
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

IF YES

[INSECURITY2] What challenges around housing insecurity have you experienced? (select all that apply)

- Difficulty or inability to pay rent or mortgage
- Eviction threat or eviction order
- Crowded housing conditions
- Frequent moving
- Unsafe or insufficient housing conditions
- Being unhoused
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

Experience of Natural Hazards

[EXPERIENCE_FLD] In the past 5 years, have you ever experienced any of the following after a flood? (select all that apply)

- Damage to home due to flooding
- Damage to property due to flooding
- Displacement from home due to flooding
- None of the above
- I have never had a flood experience
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

IF YES (displaced)

[DISTANCE] How far did you have to go to find housing?

- Within the same city
- To a different city within the same state
- To a different state
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer.

[DURATION] How long were you displaced from your home?

- A few days
- A few weeks to a month
- Between 1 and 6 months
- More than 6 months
- I never returned to my original home
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[FLOOD_HEALTH] Have you ever experienced negative health effects due to flooding? (Select all that apply)

- Wounds or other physical injuries
- Respiratory infection
- Allergic reactions
- Stress or other mental health challenges
- Prefer to describe:
- No
- Prefer not to answer

[EXPERIENCE_HEAT] In the past 5 years, have you ever experienced extreme heat that you were not able to find relief from?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

{COOLING} Do you have access to reliable AC in your home?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[TEMPERATURE_COST] Have you ever experienced financial stress or struggled to pay to maintain a comfortable temperature in your home?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[HEAT_HEALTH] Have you ever experienced negative health effects due to extreme heat?
Select all that apply.

- Heat stress
- Heat stroke
- Dehydration
- Stress or other mental health challenges
- Prefer to describe:
- No
- Prefer not to answer

IF YES

[HOSPITALIZATION] Did you ever have to go to a doctor or be hospitalized as a result of heat exposure?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[MEDICATION] Do you currently use any medication that must be maintained at a specific temperature?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[PREV_SERVICES] Have you ever attempted to access emergency services after a natural disaster (flooding or heat wave)?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

IF YES

[WHAT_SERVICES] What services did you access via government, non-profit, mutual aid, or other sources? (select all that apply)

- Temporary shelter (e.g., a Red Cross shelter, shelter at a community center or religious center, etc.)
- Food assistance (e.g., free meals or groceries, Disaster Supplement Nutrition Assistance Program (D-SNAP) benefits, etc.)
- Monetary assistance (e.g., FEMA Individuals and Households program funds, community donations, etc.)
- Emergency medical assistance
- Fire or police services
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

If no, why not?

- Did not know where to go to access services
- Fear of discrimination or violence
- Doubts over eligibility
- Did not need assistance
- Tried to but was denied
- Tried to but was unable to complete the process (too difficult to navigate the process)
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

Emergency Services

Likert scale questions (strongly disagree to strongly agree):

- I would face discrimination on the basis of my sexuality and/or gender identity if I were to try to access emergency services
- I would face violence on the basis of my sexuality and/or gender identity if I were to try to access emergency services
- If I had to leave my home as a result of a flooding event, I would know where to go
- If I had to leave my home as a result of a flooding event, I would have access to safe housing
- If I had to leave my home as a result of a flooding event, I would have access to food
- If I had to leave my home as a result of a flooding event, I would be worried about violence
- If I had to leave my home as a result of extreme heat, I would know where to go
- If I had to leave my home as a result of extreme heat, I would have access to safe housing

- If I had to leave my home as a result of extreme heat, I would have access to food
- If I had to leave my home as a result of extreme heat, I would be worried about violence
- I am worried about climate change.
- Climate-related disasters (such as heat and flooding) could negatively impact my access to gender affirming care.

[SERVICES_FUTURE] Which of the following services would you feel comfortable utilizing if you were impacted by a climate-related disaster (flooding or heat) in the future?

- Temporary shelter
- Food assistance
- Monetary assistance
- Emergency medical assistance
- Fire or police services
- Prefer to describe:
- Prefer not to answer

[BARRIERS_FUTURE] What do you imagine would be barriers to you accessing emergency services in the future?

- Do not know where to go to access services
- Fear of discrimination or violence
- Too difficult to navigate the process
- Do not need assistance
- Prefer to describe:
- None
- Prefer not to answer

[FUTURE_HELP] If you were impacted by a disaster, who would you turn to for help? [select all that apply]

- Friends or chosen family
- Biological family
- Community organizations
- Government program
- Prefer to describe:
- None
- Prefer not to answer

[END] Is there anything else that you would like to share about your experiences of climate-related disasters or any other aspect of this survey? (open ended)

